

ClairCity Top Trumps

**Run the city
on wind energy**

- Easy**
- Cheap**
- Fast**
- Green**

**Take the bus to school,
for shopping and hobbies**

- Easy** 3
- Cheap** 5
- Fast** 5
- Green** 7

ClairCity Top Trumps

How do our behaviours shape our environment? What makes the air in our towns and cities clean? And what makes it dirty?

Find out as you play ClairCity Top Trumps. Create your cards and play with friends, family or schoolmates.

www.claircity.eu/take-action/educator

Use these icons or create your own

Instructions

We have the power to improve our air and our climate. Use these cards to talk through possible solutions to air pollution and climate change, and rank which solutions are the best for people and the environment.

Now create your own cards, by scoring your solutions for each attribute. Use a scale from 1 to 10, where 1 is worst, and 10 is the best.

To start the game, shuffle and deal all the cards face down. Each player holds their cards so that they can see the top cards only.

The player to the dealers' left starts by reading out a attribute from the top card (e.g. easy, cheap). The other player(s) then read out the same attribute from their card(s). The winner of the round is the person with the biggest number for that attribute.

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Can you find the least polluted route? Help your friends reduce their exposure to air pollution and make their way safely to school

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**Take the bus to school,
for shopping and hobbies**

Easy	3
Cheap	5
Fast	5
Green	7

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Buy an electric car

Easy	4
Cheap	1
Fast	8
Green	6

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Easy
Cheap
Fast
Green

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Clean Air Top Trumps

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**Easy
Cheap
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